

FINE EFFECTS IN EPOXY BINDERS OF POLYMER COMPOSITE MATERIALS AFTER EXPOSURE TO THE SPACE ENVIRONMENT

Oleg V. Startsev¹, A. Paillous², V.V. Isupov¹, A.S. Krotov¹, and E.F. Nikishin³

¹ *Altai State University, 66 Dimitrova St., Barnaul, 656099, Russia*

² *CERT-ONERA/DESP, 2 Avenue E. Belin, Toulouse, 31055 cedex, France*

³ *M.V. Khrunitchev State Space Scientific Production Center ("Salyut" Design Bureau), 18 Novozavodskaya St., Moscow, 121087, Russia*

SUMMARY: Physical and mechanical properties of polymer composite materials on the basis of epoxy binders being used in aircraft and space technics and subjected to the low Earth orbit space environment influence have been investigated by the DMA method. New spectrometric approach was suggested for processing of dependences of the dynamic shear modulus on the temperature, in particular, numerical derivation and decomposition of first derivative curves into Gauss distribution. To raise the reliability of determination of fine gradient effects of binder properties across the thickness of the laminates, computer analysis of DMA data according to the spectrometric principles was performed, conclusions about stability of the materials in the structure of micrometeor protection of "Mir" orbital complex were made.

KEYWORDS: space exposure, dynamic mechanical analysis, numerical derivation, Gauss distribution, gradient of properties, thermal cycling, α -transition region, postcuring process.

INTRODUCTION

Different thermal methods like linear dilatometry, differential scanning calorimetry, etc. are being used in investigations of polymer composite materials (PCM). In the group of these methods the dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) gives the most detailed information about mechanical and thermophysical characteristics of PCM. In particular, it is widely used for identification of physical and chemical processes in the epoxy binders of composites under influence of outer space factors and in simulated low Earth orbit space environment [1-5].

It is well-known that the traditional way to determine parameters of relaxation processes and transitions of the epoxy binders is analysis of $G' = f(T)$, $\text{tg } \delta = f(T)$ and $c_l = f(T)$ dependences measured by the DMA method. At the temperatures corresponding to revealing of a new type of molecular mobility one can see temperature transitions in the form of breaks on the curves of dynamic shear modulus G' and of low-frequency sound velocity c_l . Shifts of characteristic temperatures of the α -transition region (glass transition temperatures in the disordered matrix

of the binder T_{g1} and in more ordered regions T_{g2}) are usually analyzed [1-3], that allows to judge about relaxation processes peculiar to the material and to predict changes in its chemical and physical properties. Making a more careful analysis it is succeeded to discover several transitions corresponding to revealing of separated macrochains and molecular groups [2].

To determine the $T_1 - T_3$, $T_2 - T_4$ temperature boundaries earlier we applied the graphic derivation method by means of tangent lines built manually, which now is considered unacceptable to be used because of subjective errors raising up to 30 %. Therefore, potentialities of dynamic mechanical spectrometry significantly depend on sensitivity of the used equipment and on resolution the DMA-spectra mathematical processing methods. In the present paper it is suggested to take boundaries of the α -transition region and value of the temperature derivative of dynamic bending and shear modulus determined by principles of dynamic mechanical spectrometry for new quantitative criteria of state of the binder, a set of parameters to obtain the most complete information about relaxation and transition processes in the binders under the outer space factors influence is reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

DMA data of a large series of PCM exposed to the space environment for a long time and then retrieved to Earth for further laboratory study are discussed in this paper. One experiment included KMU-3l, KMU-3ln, KMU-4l carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP), VPS-7v glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) and their compounds with several variants of surface protection: aluminium foil, aluminium alloy, glass netting, lacquer and paint coating exposed to space on the surfaces of "Salyut" and "Mir" orbital stations for a number of time periods (Table 1). This experiment is conducted by M.V. Khrunitchev State Space Scientific Production Center (Moscow, Russia). Holders with the samples during the space exposure were placed in the frames fixed rigidly 50 mm from the body of the adapter module. The exposure conditions correspond to the altitude of 300–500 km and are considered in [2].

Table 1: List of PCM exposed to a low Earth orbit space environment

Denomination	Geometrical dimensions, mm	Time of exposure, days	Number of thermocycles
KMU-3l KMU-3l/KMU-3l	33×8×1.3 33×8×(1.3+1.3)	304; 382; 686; 102; 456; 1501	4864; 6112; 10976; 1632; 7296; 24016
VPS-7v/VPS-7v	33×8×(1.15+1.15)	102; 456; 1501	1632; 7296; 24016
KMU-3ln "Slocarbon"	66×50×0.46 58×51×0.46	456 1024	7296 16384
VPS-7v	95×5×2	304; 382; 686	4864; 6112; 10976
VPS-7v/KMU-4l VPS-7v/KMU-3l	33×8×(1.15+1.3)	102; 456; 1024; 1501	1632; 7296; 16384; 24016
KMU-4l	58×8×1.2 58×8×2.4	102; 456; 1024; 1501	1632; 7296; 16384; 24016

Another experiment was carried out on the board of "Mir" orbital station by CNES and CERT-ONERA/DESP (Toulouse, France). The French experiment was called "Echantillons", it consisted of four panels exposed to vacuum, O-atoms and UV radiation for 13 months.

Appropriate analysis has been conducted on three composites: GY70/V108, HMS/B914 and HMS/DAO 506 available in the initial state and after the flight experiment, and on the G50/6376 composite material in the initial state.

The essence of the employed DMA method as applied to PCM consists in determining of temperature dependences of dynamic shear modulus G' , mechanical loss tangent $\text{tg } \delta$ and low-frequency sound velocity c_t with the help of a reversible torsion pendulum [2,4]. The temperature interval of measurements ranged between 20-300 °C. The error in finding the characteristics of G' , c_t and $\text{tg } \delta$ did not exceed 2.5-3 %. These measurements were made at Batumi Branch of the All-Union Institute of Aviation Materials and later at Barnaul State Pedagogical University and described in a number of papers and scientific technical reports.

Testing at CERT-ONERA/DESP was performed on a Polymer Laboratories "Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analyser" facility (PL-DMTA) used in a dual cantilever configuration [3]. Specimens have been measured from -150 °C to nearly 300 °C on two frequencies of 1 Hz and 10 Hz; the test was made in two passages: upward and backward in the temperature range. The experiment error was about 1 %.

All specimens were dried beforehand at 70 ± 5 °C in a thermal chamber. Geometrical dimensions of the rectangular-shaped samples used for the DMA averaged to $60 \times 10 \times h$ and to $50 \times 10 \times h$ for the PL-DMTA (h is the thickness of the samples) and were controlled using a micrometer instrument with high accuracy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mathematical Model of the Spectrometric Processing

A temperature dependence of dynamic shear modulus G' is smoothed with the help of cubic splines [6] with weights

$$w_k = a \cdot \left[2 \cdot \left(\frac{Y_{k+1} - Y_k}{h_{k+1}} - \frac{Y_k - Y_{k-1}}{h_k} \right) / \left((h_{k+1} + h_k) + \frac{1}{h_k} \right) \right], \quad (1)$$

where a is coefficient of proportionality, $y_k = (G'_{k-1} + G'_k + G'_{k+1})/3$, $h_k = (T_k - T_{k-1})$, $k = 2, \dots, n-1$, n is number of experimental points. Coefficient of smoothing of the spline p is found from minimum of the function [7]

$$F \equiv \sum_{k=1}^n \left[(f_k - G'_k)^2 + \frac{\partial^2 f_k}{\partial T_k^2} \right] \xrightarrow{p} \text{m in.} \quad (2)$$

Afterwards, the smoothed dependence of the dynamic shear modulus $f_k(T_k)$ is derivated and the first derivative curve $\partial f_k / \partial T_k$ is decomposed into Gauss distribution [8] (Fig. 1):

$$\Phi = \sum_{k=1}^n (v_k - \partial f_k / \partial T_k)^2, \quad (3)$$

$$v_k = \sum_{j=1}^m g_{jk}, \quad g_{jk} = a_j \exp \left[-\ln(2.0) \frac{(b_j - T_k)^2}{c_j^2} \right],$$

where a_j is intensity of a peak j , b_j is abscissa of the central point (temperature center T_c) of a peak j , c_j is a parameter equal to half-width of a peak j , T_k is temperature, m is amount of peaks. These parameters are found by Fletcher-Rivce's method of conjugate gradients [6].

To determine the first approximation for $\{a_j^{(0)}, b_j^{(0)}, c_j^{(0)}, j=1, \dots, m\}$ the fourth derivative $\partial^4 f_k / \partial T_k^4$ is built (if the second derivative $\partial^2 f_k / \partial T_k^2$ is used, errors are resulted very gross). $b_j^{(0)}$ is found from the equation $\partial^4 f_k / \partial T_k^4 = 0$, $a_j^{(0)}$ is determined as $\gamma \partial f_k / \partial T_k$ ($\gamma < 1$), and $c_j^{(0)}$ is equal to half-distance from the first maximum to the first minimum of $\partial^4 f_k / \partial T_k^4$ around the point $b_j^{(0)}$.

Fig. 1: Illustration of a typical spectrometric processing of DMA curves. Smoothing of the experimental dependence $G'(T)$ and following decomposition of the derivative curve in the form of a finite amount of Gauss peaks

In general, the dG'/dT curve in the region of α -relaxation is approximated by n Gauss peaks. This situation, obviously, corresponds to the case when the α -transition region represents a superposition of several overlapped processes in binder micromatrices ordered with different rates because each peak means a process of molecular mobility revealing itself under certain conditions. Using parameters of the Gauss processes several criteria for determining the T_{g1} , T_{g2} and $T_1 - T_4$ binder characteristic temperatures which are usually discussed were tested.

The following ones have been chosen for further quantitative analysis of numerous DMA curves:

$$T_{g1} = b_n - 2c_n, T_{g2} = b_1 + 2c_1, \quad (4)$$

$$T_1 = b_1 - 2c_1, T_2 = b_{k+1} - 2c_{k+1}, T_3 = b_k + 2c_k, T_4 = b_n + 2c_n,$$

where k is the last peak located in the α -transition region and $\frac{d^2G'}{dT^2}(b_k) < 0$.

$$\text{If } n=1 \text{ then } T_{g1} = b - c, T_{g2} = b + c, T_1 = b - 2c, T_2 = b - c, T_3 = b + c, T_4 = b + 2c. \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2: Correlation of the $T_1 - T_4$ characteristic temperatures determined by the classical method from $c_i = f(T)$ curves [1,2] and using the spectrometric principles

These methods and algorithms have been incorporated into a software suite for IBM PC. Correlation coefficients of the T_{g1} , T_{g2} and $T_2 - T_4$ temperatures calculated by the traditional way and from the formulae (4) and (5) are not less than 0.91. Data shown in Fig. 2 were obtained for 49 PCM samples in the initial state and after different types of space exposure.

Peculiarities of Relaxation Processes in the Epoxy Binders

It is well-known due to which factors properties of PCM can change during a space exposure. For instance, it has been ascertained in [1-5] that regimes of thermal cycling cause the epoxy binder postcuring process and this fact is corroborated with a rise in the binder glass transition temperature.

Fig. 3, 4 show evolution of processes in the binder of KMU-3l CFRP discovered after the approximation of dependences $G'(T)$ by the above-described mathematical algorithm. The shifts of the T_{g1} , T_{g2} and T_c values towards the higher temperatures (Table 2) are consistent with such conceptions of aging of PCM in the space environment. A comparative study points out that with the increase in time of exposure the binder tends to raise its structural homogeneity level, the α -transition region becomes symmetrical and it can be approximated only by one Gauss peak (see the derivative curves of $G'(T)$ for 456 and 1501 days of exposure). In other words, the magnitude of the effects being investigated depends for the most part on the amount of thermocycles obtained by the materials in space.

We have proved earlier in [5] that a combined and competitive effect of erosion etching and thermal cycling in space leads to a difference in postcuring of the binder and the formation of the mechanical properties gradient across the thickness of the laminates. This effect is observed on the spectrometric curves for two couples of the KMU-3ln compounds exposed for 456 days in two layers and discovering only one process in the binder (Table 3). The increases in T_{g1} of the irradiated samples 1.4-2.2 times higher than those for the non-irradiated samples facing the body of the station, in which a decrease of T_{g2} after the exposure is seen.

Fig. 3: Evolution of relaxation processes in KMU-4l CFRP of $(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)$ laying during a long-time space exposure

Table 2: T_c , T_{g1} and T_{g2} characteristic temperatures of KMU-4l CFRP of $(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)$ and $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$ laying determined from the spectrometric principles (see Fig. 3, 4)*

	T_{g1} , °C	T_{g2} , °C	ΔT_{g1} , °C	ΔT_{g2} , °C	T_c , °C process 1	T_c , °C process 2	T_c , °C process 3
Reference sample	130	177	0	0	138	166	201
	130	176	0	0	–	153	203

102 days of exposure	137 136	178 184	7 6	1 8	144 –	174 160	210 –
456 days of exposure	152 155	191 195	22 25	14 19	– –	172 175	– 206
1501 days of exposure	– 162	– 203	– 32	– 27	– –	– 183	– –

* Dashes signify absence of a sample or of a process

The behaviour of GFRP/GFRP and GFRP/CFRP hybrid composites in space (Table 4) submits to the general tendencies very well. It should be accented that even if the Tables 3, 4 are not accompanied with figures, they give complete information about transitions in the binders because the presented indices are calculated on the basis of the criteria (4) and (5).

Fig. 4: Evolution of relaxation processes in KMU-4l CFRP of (0°/90°) laying during a long-time space exposure

The study shows that on the application of micrometeor protection panels on "Mir" orbital station there is no reduction of mechanical strength in KMU-3l, KMU-4l coverings, as well as postcuring processes predominate over destruction, which creates additional strength for micrometeor protection structures of the station.

Table 3: T_{g1} and T_{g2} characteristic temperatures of two couples of KMU-3ln CFRP exposed to the space environment for 456 days in two layers

	T_{g1} , °C	T_{g2} , °C	ΔT_{g1} , °C	ΔT_{g2} , °C	Temperature center T_c , °C
Reference sample	122	166	0	0	144
Irradiated	144	175	22	9	159

sample	137	173	15	7	155
Non-irradiated sample	132	163	10	-3	148
	133	164	11	-2	148

A number of exposed samples is always very limited, therefore in order to extend information about the mechanical properties the PL-DMTA was performed on two frequencies and in two passages in the temperature range. The accuracy which the bending modulus E' is measured with depends upon the chosen frequency, that is a feature of the PL-DMTA facility.

Table 5 lists the spectrometric parameters for the binder softening region of the HMS/B914 material for the reference and flight samples. In all cases for the both samples the relaxation taking place in the binder is approximated by one Gauss process. Temperature positions of this process are evidently different on the applied frequencies but very close to each other for the first and the second passages of the PL-DMTA testing. Temperatures of $\text{tg } \delta$ maximums placed in brackets in Table 5 correlate with T_c values with a coefficient 1.02-1.05. As it was noticed earlier, the results may always be affected by possible errors owing to a fluctuation of properties from sample to sample and from measurement to measurement.

Table 4: T_{g1} and T_{g2} characteristic temperatures of VPS-7v/VK-9/VPS-7v (Hybrid 1) and VPS-7v/VK-9/KMU-3l (Hybrid 2) composite compounds

		$T_{g1}, ^\circ\text{C}$	$T_{g2}, ^\circ\text{C}$	$\Delta T_{g1}, ^\circ\text{C}$	$\Delta T_{g2}, ^\circ\text{C}$	Temperature center $T_c, ^\circ\text{C}$
Hybrid 1	Reference sample	63	103	0	0	83
	1501 days of exposure	81	116	18	13	98
Hybrid 2	Reference sample	75	117	0	0	96
	102 days of exposure	86	129	11	12	108
	1501 days of exposure	94	130	19	13	112

Half-width parameters c can be accepted for a characteristic of the relaxation speed and for an index of homogeneity of the binder. Comparison of the Δc values which are unchanged after the 13-months exposure does not allow to speak about any variations in the crosslinking density. Meantime, as the consideration indicates, a competitive phenomenon of the chemical activity growth is progressing. Such a tendency is seen from analysis of the presented Δa values of the α -transition peaks (Table 5, 1 passage). At the same time single comparison of the intensities a with one another does not point out a strict regularity.

Table 5: Temperature parameters of relaxation processes in the binder of HMS/B914 CFRP

		Temperature center T_c (max $\text{tg } \delta$), $^\circ\text{C}$		Half-width of the processes c , $^\circ\text{C}$		Intensity of the processes a	
		1 Hz	10 Hz	1 Hz	10 Hz	1 Hz	10 Hz
Reference sample	1 passage	233 (239)	241 (245)	19	20	36	31
	2 passage	234 (245)	242 (255)	27	28	45	38

Flight sample	1 passage 2 passage	238 (243) 236 (248)	245 (252) 244 (256)	19 27	20 25	47 41	43 32
$\Delta T_c, \Delta c, \Delta a$ 1 passage, °C		5	4	0	0	11	12
$\Delta T_c, \Delta c, \Delta a$ 2 passage, °C		2	2	0	-3	-4	-6

The appropriate computer analysis for PL-DMTA data of the three other composites was performed. With the infrequent exceptions, the region of α -relaxation in the case of both frequencies and passages is approximated by two processes. Sets of the relaxation processes are illustrated in Fig. 5-7.

Fig. 5: Temperature positions of the first (left) and the second (right) processes in the binder

Fig. 6: Half-width parameters of the first (left) and the second (right) processes in the binder

Fig. 7: Intensities of the first (left) and the second (right) processes in the binder

As regards the general situation, there is an opposite but an incontestable regularity of a distinction in temperature positions of the both processes in the first and the second passages of the PL-DMTA testing but their values are very close to each other on the applied frequencies. The effect of the binder postcuring is proved by positive shifts of positions of the processes (glass transition temperatures T_c) after the flight experiment. The stable growths in T_c (Fig. 5) and negative values of Δa (Table 5) obtained in the second passages in comparison with those in the first passages are explained by complementary postcuring because of heating up to 300 °C during the test. Narrowing of the α -transition region seen from decrease of the half-width parameters in most cases in Fig. 6 is a consequence of the conception about transitions in the PCM binders.

CONCLUSION

New principles were implemented for processing and decoding of experimental results obtained by the DMA. The suggested spectrometric methodology provides high accuracy and sufficient quantitative correlation with already reported results. Physical interpretation of the spectrometric characteristics for a set of relaxation processes in the binder allowed to discover new criteria for definition of binder glass transition temperature. Efficiency of the considered principles is illustrated on the example of investigation of the epoxy binder postcuring process in carbon and glass reinforced plastics after some direct exposures to space environment. The observed changes in the parameters of relaxation processes during the exposure clearly evidence complex and intensive transformations occurring in the PCM binders due to the binder crosslinking effect at the expense of reserve unresponsive epoxy groups.

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